

THE INTERPRITATIONS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR TRANSLATION EQUALENTS

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Abstract: This article is aimed at discussing the issues of phraseology and their interpretation in linguistics and considering alternative options, and as an object of research, which is analyzing phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages. Research methods such as associative, conceptual, contextual, component, lexicographic, linguistic, cultural, semantic cognitive, etymological analysis were used in the exploration. This study presents an analysis of the methodologies used in the translation of idiomatic expressions and phraseological units into English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: phraseological unit, phrasis-expression, speech wrapper, stability, set phrases, false friend.

Introduction: The field of linguistics is like a giant tree. it consists of many branches and each branch consist of many more sections. Especially, in the field of linguistics, translation studies is developing from year to year, but it also causes some problems. Translation studies certainly requires great responsibility and skill from every interpreter. When translating information from one language into another, the translator must know the morphology and syntax of these two languages, or the culture, proverbs, phraseological units, expressions of the speakers of this language. While translating simple sentences is not difficult, translating expressions, proverbs and phraseological units in the language requires considerable skill. Because the above units stated in one language may have a completely different meaning in the second language and the reader may misunderstand the information due to direct translation. One of the theories uses the consideration of phraseological units as a cultural phenomenon in translation studies. As a result, phraseology requires studying the field of sociolinguistics. Phraseological units serve a very special and significant purpose. They make it possible to communicate ideas clearly and succinctly, and they lend utterances a semantic complexity that would be challenging, if not impossible, to do through other channels. At this stage of our research, we will consider the cultural specificity of English and Uzbek phraseological units.

Main Part.

Phraseology is defined as the study of the structural features of phraseological units, their appearance in the language system, and the properties of their use at a point. Although the term "phraseology" is derived from the Greek word "phrasia" (phrasis-expression, speech wrapper), this term serves to express different meanings. (Radjabovich, 2024) The use of phrases in linguistics allows the speaker to use prefabricated quotations that are rarely worn with humor, sarcasm, or insight. Phraseological units, in contrast other vocabulary units, have their own national stamp and reveal details about the history, culture, and people of the nation. Phraseologisms, which are the product of long-term development, reflect the experience of society and pass it from one generation to another, so they play an important role not only as a means of communication, but also as a source of various socially significant information. If we consider the interpretation of Uzbek and English languages in the study of phraseological units. First of all, let's find out the meaning of the word interpretation. Interpretation means action of explaining the meaning of something, the way something is explained or understood. A language interpreter or sign language interpreter must not only quickly and carefully interpret meaning, but also tone and intent of the original message into the target or interpreted language. So, interpretation is a tool that shows the true skill of the translator. As mentioned above, if we discuss the interpretation of phraseological units in Uzbek and English languages, it should be noted that translating phraseological units depends on twice as much knowledge, experience and responsibility from the translator. Finding the exact equivalent of a combination of words in one language with one meaning in another language is often a problem. As a result, the translated text message cannot fully retain its meaning. To solve these problems, scientists have been conducting scientific research since the beginning of the twentieth century. The first researcher of phraseological theory was Charles Balli. He included in his scientific works special chapters on the study of phraseological units. Phraseological compounds consist mainly of word combinations, in other words, phraseologies are a separate unit of language that includes figurative, fixed word combinations that are completely or partially semantically reshaped, equal in structure to a free link or sentence. Most of the phraseologies were created by the people in both English and other languages, their authors are unknown, and their sources of origin are not clear. In this sense, the phraseological scholar A.V. The author of most of the English phraseologies of the day is unknown, and has reasonably pointed out the idea that they were created by the people. However,

it is possible to identify the sources of origin of some phraseological units. In this sense, phraseology is a microsystem that is part of the general system of language, which reflects the heritage and values of the past, passed down from generation to generation. Many of the phraseological units that make up the system are a source of enrichment for a particular language. The phraseological system consists of the phraseological units, the relationship between their main components. Phraseologisms are connections of words that consist of more than one word and are stable in meaning and form. (Radjabovich, 2024) V. According to Kunin, it is characterized as a unit with a stable property. Linguists' views on stagnation do not coincide, because when they say phraseological units stagnation, they mean its ready use. The concept of stagnation is important for phraseology because the solution of most theoretical and practical problems in phraseology is directly related to this concept. In order to consider an alternative option in the interpretation and translation of phraseological units, it is permissible to first refer to the view of linguists that include phraseological units. For example, the lexicographical and linguistic study of phraseology is multifaceted, especially in translation into English and Uzbek languages. Phraseology is so important in language that it plays a decisive role in understanding and conveying subtleties of language. Every language, including Uzbek and English, has a collection of phraseology that can cause great difficulties in translation. For example:.

Linguistics: From a linguistic point of view, the study of phraseology involves understanding their syntactic, semantic and pragmatic aspects. This includes how phraseological units are structured, their literal and figurative meanings, and how they are used in communication. Linguistic research also involves understanding the cultural contexts that give rise to these phraseology.

The above mentioned are examples of some challenges in translating phraseological units.

Lexicographic Aspects: Lexicography involves writing and editing dictionaries. In the context of English and Uzbek phraseology, lexicography focuses on the coordination of these phraseological units and their meanings, usage and translations. This is especially difficult because phraseology often contains cultural, historical, and idiomatic meanings that cannot be easily translated.

Non-equivalence: Often, there is no direct equivalent for a phraseology in the target language. Translators must either find a close approximation or rephrase it while maintaining the original meaning and impact.

Cultural Specifics: Many phraseologies are deeply rooted in the culture and history of their language of origin. This makes translation challenging, as the translator needs to find equivalent expressions in the target language that convey the same meaning and cultural essence.

Role of Technology: Advances in computational linguistics and AI have aided in translating and studying phraseologies. Machine translation systems, however, still struggle with accurately translating idiomatic expressions and culturally specific phraseologies. (Oybekovna, 2024)

English and Uzbek Context: The translation between these two languages is fascinating due to their unique linguistic roots (German and Turkish respectively) and cultural background. Each language has its unique set of expression and idioms that reflect its history, culture and social norms. The study of phraseology in the context of translation into English and Uzbek languages provides insight into the languages themselves, the culture and thought processes of the peoples who speak them. It is an interdisciplinary work that connects linguistics, cultural studies, and translation theory.

Contextual Usage: Understanding the context in which a phraseology is used is crucial. This includes not only the linguistic context but also the situational and cultural contexts.

Methodology:

In this article, regardless of the literary source of Uzbek phraseology, phraseological units that can be equivalent to them in English translation are considered. Phraseological units make our speech more precise, and more vivid, diverse, and expressive. According to some linguists, the role of phraseologism in the formation of language and culture is extremely important. Such an attractive stable layer of the language includes the basic values, social ethics, and national culture that are unique to each nation.

Results:

Phraseological units include idioms, compound sentences, proverbs, grammatical phraseological units, especially the scope of English and Uzbek phraseology is large and diverse. If we study the classification of English phraseological units in connection with the Uzbek language.

Structural classification: A. The main component of substantive phraseological units is the noun. For example: a drop in the bucket (drop in the bucket); Box and Cox (alternating); wind bag (philosopher); battle-ax, etc.

B. Verb Phrases: Phraseologisms functionally connected with the verb. For example: to play it cool (behave calmly, coolly); to talk big (boast); to break a bubble (expose the true face); to be in the pot (drunk); to make mountains of mokehills (much ado about nothing), etc.

C. Adjective phraseological units are phraseological units whose main component is an adjective, and the share of adjectives in the total volume of studied phraseological units is very small.

D. Phraseologisms with a sentence structure There are phraseological units in the English language that are structurally connected with a sentence. Phraseological units that are structured according to the structure of a simple sentence and have components connected as a subject and a predicate are considered typical. For example: he has no guts (he is a worthless person, he is worthless); you said it (I totally agree with you); etc.(Abduvaxidovna, 2021)

Complete coincidence of form and context in phrasiological units is rarely met with. 1. Black frost (phrase me) – qorasovuq. 2. To bring oil to fire (idiom) – alanga yog’ quymoq.(Esanova, 2024)

Like many other languages, Uzbek is rich in stable word combinations, including humorous and ironic expressions, allusions, hints, ethical expressions, blessings, ethnographisms, and folklorisms. These are not only content-rich but also have an external cultural character (Table 1). Table 1. Comparative Table of Uzbek Phrases and Their English.

Uzbek phrase	English phrase
dunyo turguncha turing	live long and prosper
yotigi bilan tushuntirmoq	to speak cautiously
oramizda qolsin	Between you and me
dong qotib uxlamoq	To be fast asleep
Ikki og’iz gap	a couple of words
Ignani ustida o’tirgandek bo’lmoq	to be on pins and needles
bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmoq	with a single heart
ish qaritmaydi, g’am qaritadi	care killed the cat
kechasi bilan uxlamasdan ishlamoq	burn the midnight oil
O’lim ostonasida	at the death's door
Temirni qizig’ida bos	Strike while iron is hot
Muhim inson	big wig
bir o’q bilan ikki quyonni urmoq	kill two birds with one stone;

Discussions:

To conclude, phraseological units in Uzbek are divided into two types: phraseological unity and phraseological fusion, in English — according to phraseological unity and phraseological fusion, phraseological combinations or expressions. In this article, we considered the translation of phraseological units into English and Uzbek and their equivalents. We witnessed the problems with their translation and the existence of different translation methods. In different situations, the interpreter may use different approaches based on his personality. The translator must feel a part of the translated culture, immerse himself in it, create the only possible and at the same time unique version of the translation. For this, the interpretation should incorporate many realities of foreign culture into its thinking and reveal the full power and richness of the native language.

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